

Social Barriers And Women's Political Empowerment In District Bajaur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract: *This study investigate the social barriers affecting women's political empowerment in Bajaur District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Despite constitutional guarantees and policy efforts to enhance gender equity and equality, female involvement in the political activities remains neglected due to restricted mobility, traditional gender role, purdah (veiling), limited access to resources and patriarchal norms. The study found that women face more restrictions than men in the political process. The chi-square test was used to assess the association between independent and dependent variable (social barriers with women's political empowerment). This study employed a quantitative research design and collected primary data from 375 household heads through a structured questionnaire. The study concluded that despite constitutional and structural provisions guaranteeing women's political participation, various social barriers hinder the implementation of these provisions. The study results indicate a significant relationship between women's political empowerment and social barriers such as traditional gender role, Purdah (Veiling), Patriarchal norms, family influence religious misinterpretation, ignorance, no political awareness, and restricted mobility. The study recommends advocacy campaigns to raise awareness about gender inclusion, promote women's political roles, and include them in policy interventions at the community level, with a focus on education. Moreover, these findings contribute to the broader discourse on gender and political participation in developing societies and provide empirical evidence for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to strengthen democratic inclusion.*

Keywords: Social barriers, Women Political Empowerment

Introduction

Women have the greatest potential to do great things in the entire world. However, it is rare for women to progress in life without encouragement and support (Applewhite & Levy, 2026). Women's empowerment in politics refers to making sure they participate actively and vocally in political leadership, governance, and decision-making (Moghadam & Gheyntanchi, 2010). It addresses women's engagement in political rights, equal representation in the political system, and the elimination of structural obstacles that prevent women from engaging in politics. Political empowerment is necessary for inclusive governance and gender equality (Das, et al., 2025; Panday, 2013). There are broadly two

sexes (male and female) found in every society. Despite the fact that their professions vary across the world, they are still required to make constructive contributions to society. There are two sexes (male and female) in every society. In developing countries, it is not just men who engage in tasks that require strength, which is typically associated with men. In fact, women are more likely than men to carry heavy loads and carry water. (Robson , 2013). In most societies, especially in developing countries, women are primarily responsible for managing domestic tasks, whereas men dominate the outdoor activities such as public and political spheres. Biological differences between men and women are the cause of these discrepancies. After giving birth, Mother have to breastfeed their newborns. This maternal role forced women to remain engaged in domestic chores, while men participated in most socio-economic activities (Stromquist, 2015).

In most developing countries, girls are given lower status than boys and are given fewer rights, opportunities, and childhood benefits. Women are subjected to discrimination from an early age and fight valiantly to overcome it (Rafferty, 2013). Women in Pakistan face discrimination from birth. When a girl is born, the mother is usually blamed, and there is often disappointment and even anger from the family. Girls generally have less access to food, health care, and education than boys. As a result, girls are more likely to die from childhood diseases (Hamid, 2010). There is very little funding for girls' education and skills development. In some societies, a daughter is considered a liability. Thus, a girl is taught from a young age that she is only a temporary member of the family and that any skills she learns will benefit her in-laws more than her own family. Chaaban et al., (2011) reported that girls pursuing vocational training have fewer chances of becoming teachers in these institutions due to lack of funding and career opportunities. The philosophy of women's liberation is dominated by liberal feminism, which claims that women do not have equal rights in Pakistan or anywhere else. Pakistani women live in a complex and frightening environment that presents both chances and obstacles. While on the other hand, female representation has been operationalized by constitutional provisions that reserve seats for women in the Senate, National Assembly, and local government structures (Khan & Naqvi, 2020; Jabeen et al., 2019). Patriarchal traditions are well entrenched and have the potential to significantly limit the participation of many women in the political process, due to cultural factors as well as lack of resources and education (Kollo & Sunarso, 2018; Wayan & Nyoman, 2020). Threats of political violence and harassment are expected to accompany the dizzying world of hardships that isolate women after they gain political power in an already hostile environment (Dhesi, 2025; Krook, 2017).

However, empowering women in Pakistani politics is essential to achieving stability and democratic progress. A more inclusive political system, stronger links between policy achievements and the diverse needs of all citizens, and the legitimacy of governance can provide women with access to politics. (Shafiq et al., 2024). The veil (Purdah) affects women's mobility and, in turn, affects women's access to education and empowerment (Sultana, 2023; Sultana et al., 2009). In conservative societies like Buner, the veil (Purdah) constitutes a significant social barrier, preventing women from actively participating in the political process and assuming leadership roles. Purdah is highly practiced in pashtun area, where women are more likely to vote as an extension of familial obedience than as a civic exercise, cultural constructs like the Pakhtun proverb *Khaza ya da kor da Goor* (a woman place is either at home or in the grave) serve as an example of the gender expectations that limit female political agency (Rani, 2025). The concept of empowerment was developed with the goal of improving the quality of life for everyone through better governance, better services and economic growth. Empowerment is thus essential for the development of modern society, especially for the benefit of women (Narayan, 2015; Schild et al., 2022). While the empowerment component can take many different forms, it typically begins with elementary school education (Chuang, 2015; Lovell & Vaccaro, 2010).

According to Naz et al. (2012), the social structure was designed so that men could take advantage of it. Furthermore, the concept of gender inferiority that persists in modern culture is completely false and

unfair. Inequality serves as a small basis for these characteristics, but more research is needed to identify the cultural elements that pose a serious threat to the empowerment of Pashtun women (Bibi, 2022). Pashtuns as an ethnic group are particularly adhering to centuries-old laws that guide, redirect, and channel their daily actions. Pakhtunwali severely limits the political empowerment of women. The majority of Pakhtun society is male-dominated, which guarantees male dominance and control (Naz & Ahmad, 2012; Naz & Chaudhry, 2012; Shah, 2025). According to the Pashtun code of conduct, women are considered sensitive, and their homes are considered ideal environments for their services. The Pakhtun code of life also contains a few characteristics that are primarily associated with men, such as Ghairat (valour), Badal (revenge), Jirga (an informal power structure) and Hujra (a common guest house), etc. These characteristics are mostly associated with status, power, and authority in pashtun society. Whereas, women are associated with the characteristics of pegghor (satire) and Tor (stigma), these characteristics are typically seen as inferior and devoid of status, authority, and power. In this sense, it is clear that the Pakhtun code of life primarily hinders women's political empowerment (Hoque et al., 2026 & Naz et al., 2017).

In Pakistan, women are mostly engaged in domestic work, childcare, agricultural and reproductive work, especially in rural areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Moreover, Naz et al., (2012) highlighted that women's illiteracy and ignorance of their rights and duties in relation to politics are obstacles to women's political empowerment. According to Akhtar et al. (2020), the rigid Pashtun culture prevents women from having any independent economic involvement outside the home, therefore their contributions and share of the work are disregarded and stay unseen.

Patriarchy perpetuates gendered norms that constrain women's participation in governance and, despite extensive legislation, continues to function as a significant and often dominant force in shaping political leadership in Pakistan. Furthermore, women are primarily limited to symbolic roles or positions that contradict the traditional gender norms, which undermines their authority as leaders. Political parties marginalized women's participation in decision-making and consider them vote bank mobilisers rather than leaders. This approach therefore permanently excludes women, making it difficult for them to be represented and to be included in key policy-making roles. Furthermore, they are not well-supported in political institutions to achieve and maintain their position as leaders. In rare cases male colleagues are against female thus discriminate female politicians, which hinders their ability to influence political agendas. Many women are underrepresented in government institutions, it has become quite discouraging for many qualified women to seek political positions (Rani, 2025). The idea of "honour" has a significant impact on how society views women's involvement in politics. Women's public appearances and campaign activities are restricted due to concerns that they may undermine family or community honour. These limitations are particularly prominent in more conservative rural societies, where women who challenge social norms face resistance (Hasan, 2015). A significant cultural obstacle to women's political empowerment in Lebanon is women's ongoing attachment to family honor rather than individual agency (Good & Braden, 2014; Charred & Stephan et al., 2009; Madsen et al., 2015). Moreover, Religious misconceptions are often used as a weapon in political discourse to prevent women from participating in politics. However, conservative organizations frequently misuse religious texts to prevent women from taking on leadership positions. The perception that men make the best political decision-makers and governable bodies is reinforced by these stories (Kocht et al., 2023; Cassese et al., 2016). These misconceptions also hinder legislative changes that advance women's political rights. For instance, many religiously framed arguments opposing measures aimed at protecting women such as regulations addressing abuse and harassment often rely on misinterpreted or distorted Islamic teachings. Thus, the politics of religion limits progressive discourse and reinforces cultural barriers that keep women out of politics (Rahim, 2024; Shaheed, et al., 2010).

Women's political participation is further restricted by customs rooted in feudal and tribal traditions. Women in many parts of Pakistan are further marginalized by tribal customs that prohibit them from voting or running for office. In rural areas, male community leaders often threaten or informally agree to violate women's constitutional rights by preventing them from entering the polling place (Rani, 2025). Furthermore, it enslaves women's political agency in Pakistan's rural feudal regimes. Feudal families often select women to participate in politics, who respect patriarchal standards and do not cause trouble. This empowerment's selectivity limits women's accurate political representation and perpetuates structural inequality (Rani, 2025).

Methodology

This study investigate the social barriers affecting women's political empowerment in Bajaur District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. This study employed a quantitative research design and collected primary data from 375 household heads through a structured questionnaire using convenience sampling. The data were analyzed in SPSS. Univariate analysis was performed to summarize the distribution of the data, while chi-square analysis was used to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 1: Showing the Social Constraints to Women Political Participation

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' opinions regarding social barriers to women's political empowerment. The table shows that 284(75.7%) respondents are of the opinion that gender discrimination limit female from political participation, while 77(20.5%) respondents refuted the previous statement and 14(3.2%) had no idea about it. This assertion is supported by outcomes of Bari, (2005) that the fact is evident that women are among the vulnerable segment in society. In most developing countries, girls are given lower status than boys and are given fewer rights, opportunities, and childhood benefits. Women are subjected to discrimination from an early age and fight valiantly to overcome it (Rafferty, 2013). Women in Pakistan face discrimination from birth. When a girl is born, the mother is usually blamed, and there is often disappointment and even anger from the family. Girls generally have less access to food, health care, and education than boys. As a result, girls are more likely to die from childhood diseases (Hamid, 2010).

Furthermore, 201 (53.6%) respondents agreed that Pakhtunwali is a restraint in women political empowerment, while 174(46.4%) respondents negated the statement that purdah is not constraint to women political empowerment and 5(1.3%) have no knowledge about it. In the context of pashtun tribal area, Pakhtunwali functions as a major social barrier in limiting women involvement in political activities. Pakhtunwali severely limits the political empowerment of women (Naz & Ahmad, 2012; Naz & Chaudhry, 2012; Shah, 2025). Furthermore, 185(49.3%) of the respondents said that the delicacy nature of female hinders them from political activities, however 173(46.1%) of the respondents negate the statement, while 17(4.5%) of the respondent have no knowledge about this statement.

Moreover, majority 260(69.3%) percent of the respondents have the opinion that religious values limit females from political process, while 113(30.1%) had not buttressed the earlier statement and 2(0.5%) had no information about it. The findings of Berger et al., (2023) and Cassese et al., (2016) supported the above statement. These findings reveal that religious misconceptions are often used as a weapon in political discourse to prevent women from participating in politics. However, conservative organizations frequently misuse religious texts to prevent women from taking on leadership positions. Similarly, 253(67.5%) percent of the respondents said that Family encourage female involvement in politics, 115(30.7%) of the respondents rejected the previous statement and 7(1.9%) had no knowledge regarding this statement. Likewise, 210 (56.0%) respondents accept that patriarchal system is a constraint to women political empowerment, while 150(40.0%) respondents rejected the former statement and 15(4.0%) respondents had no knowledge about it. The studies of Kollo and Sunarso (2018) and Wayana and Nyoman, (2020) support the statement that patriarchal traditions limits the

participation of many women in the political process. Furthermore, 306(81.6%) respondents assumed that female have right of decision-making in familial affairs, while 64 (17.1%) had not in fever of the past statement and 5(1.3%) had no idea about It.

Similarly, 211(56.3%) of the respondents believed that purdah (veiling) is a barrier to women political empowerment, although 157(41.9%) respondents rejected the previous statement and 7(1.9%) didn't provide any info concerning it. Similar ideas were presented by Rani (2025) and Sultana et al., (2009) which states that the veil acts as a major social barrier in preventing women from actively engaging in political processes and leadership roles.

Likewise, 229(61.1%) of the respondents accept that Reproductive role of women restrict them from political activities, though 126(33.6%) respondents do not agree with the statement and 20(5.3%) didn't know about it. Moreover, 197(52.5%) respondents were of the opinion that Traditional gender role limit female participation in political process, while 171(45.6%) rejected the statement and 7(1.9%) had no knowledge about it. This statement is also supported by results of Naz et al., (2012) stated that women are mostly engaged in domestic work, childcare, agricultural and reproductive work, especially in rural areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, therefore they are restricted from political participation.

In addition, majority of 305(81.3%) respondents said that ignorance/ illiteracy are constraints to women political empowerment, however 63(16.8%) respondents negated the statement and the remaining 7(1.9%) had no knowledge about it. The findings of Naz et al., (2012) also supported the above statement that women's illiteracy and ignorance of their rights and duties in relation to politics are obstacles to women's political empowerment. Additionally, vast majority of 339(90.4%) respondents were of the opinion that Domestic works of female confine women from Political process, while 33(8.8%) respondent reputed the statement and 3(0.8%) didn't know about the former statement. Moreover, 275(73.3%) of the respondents were in the favour that negative attitudes of society towards involvement of women in political process, while 98(26.1%) respondents not in the favour of female involvement in politics and 2(0.5%) had no knowledge about it.

Table 1: Frequencies and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to their Perception about Social Constraints to Women Political Participation

Statement	Yes	No	Don't Know
Gender discrimination limit female from political participation	284(75.7%)	77(20.5%)	14(3.7%)
Pakhtunwali is a restraint in women political empowerment	201(53.6%)	169(46.4%)	5(1.3%)
The delicacy nature of female hinders them from political activities	185(49.3%)	173(46.1%)	17(4.5%)
Religious values limit women from political empowerment	260(69.3%)	113(30.1%)	2(0.5%)
Family encourage female involvement in politics	253(67.5%)	107(28.5%)	17(4.5%)
Patriarchal system is a constraint to women political empowerment	210(56.0%)	150(40.0%)	15(4.0%)
Female have right of decision-making in familial affairs	306(81.6%)	64(17.1%)	5(1.3%)
Purdah (veiling) is a barrier to women political empowerment	211(56.3%)	157(41.9%)	7(1.9%)
Reproductive role of women restrict them from	229(61.1%)	126(33.6%)	20(5.3%)

political activities			
Traditional gender role limit female participation in political process	197(52.5%)	171(45.6%)	7(1.9%)
Ignorance/ illiteracy are constraints to women political empowerment.	305(81.3%)	63(16.8%)	7(1.9%)
Domestic works of female confine women from Political process	339(90.4%)	33(8.8%)	3(0.8%)
There is negative attitudes of society towards involvement of women in political process	275(73.3%)	98(26.1%)	2(0.5%)

Association between Social Barriers and Women's Political Participation

To analyze the relationship between women's political empowerment and social restrictions, the perception of social constraints was limited to the statements listed in Table 2. The study displays the respondent's insight about connection among the phenomenon's that gender discrimination limit female from political participation. A significant ($p=0.004$) relationship was establish between gender discrimination with women political empowerment. The study further describes the respondent's perception between the Pakhtunwali is a restraint in women political empowerment. A significant ($p=0.000$) association was originate between Pakhtunwali is a barrier with women political empowerment. Additionally, A significant ($P=0.011$) association was found between respondent's perception that delicacy nature of female hinders them from political activities with women political empowerment. Additionally, a highly significant ($P =0.000$) association was found between respondents' perceptions that religious values prevent women from achieving political empowerment and women's political empowerment. A non-significant ($P=0.083$) relationship was discovered between respondents' view that family encourage female involvement in politics with women political empowerment. In addition, a significant ($P=0.004$) association detected patriarchal system is a constraint with women political empowerment moreover, a non-significant ($p=0.844$) association was found between female have right of decision-making in familial affairs with women political empowerment. A highly significant ($P=0.000$) relationship between purdah (veiling) is a barrier and women's political empowerment.

Furthermore, this study a significant ($p=0.0203$) relationship was discovered between reproductive role of women restrict them from political activities and political empowerment. A highly significant ($P=0.000$) association was found between that the Traditional gender role limit female participation in political process with women political empowerment. Moreover, the study indicates the respondent's perception about relationship between Ignorance/ illiteracy are constraints to women political empowerment with women political empowerment. A significant ($p=0.018$) relation was found between ignorance/ illiteracy are constraints to women political empowerment with women political empowerment.

The study further revealed the respondents' perception between domestic works of female confine women from Political process with women political empowerment. A significant ($P=0.052$) association was found that domestic works of female confine women from Political process with women political empowerment. Also, a significant ($p=0.000$) association was found between respondents' perception about negative attitudes of society towards involvement of women in political process with women political empowerment. The result shows that there is negative attitudes of society towards involvement of women in political process.

Table 2: Association between Social Barriers and Women’s Political Empowerment

Statement	Chi Square (χ^2)
Gender discrimination limit female from political participation	$\chi^2= 25.116$ (p=0.000)
Pakhtunwali is a restraint in women political empowerment	$\chi^2= 24.814$ (p=0.000)
The delicacy nature of female hinders them from political activities	$\chi^2= 12.821$ (p=0.001)
Religious values limit women from political empowerment	$\chi^2= 25.401$ (p=0.000)
Family encourage female involvement in politics	$\chi^2= 9.344$ (p=0.083)
Patriarchal system is a constraint to women political empowerment	$\chi^2= 17.300$ (p=.004)
Female have right of decision-making in familial affairs	$\chi^2= 0.310$ (p=0.844)
Purdah (veiling) is a barrier to women political empowerment	$\chi^2= 36.23$ (p=0.000)
Reproductive role of women restrict them from political activities	$\chi^2= 10.541$ (p=0.020)
Traditional gender role limit female participation in political process	$\chi^2= 31.245$ (p=0.000)
Ignorance/ illiteracy are constraints to women political empowerment.	$\chi^2= 12.980$ (p=0.018)
Domestic works of female confine women from Political process	$\chi^2= 9.479$ (p=0.052)
There is negative attitudes of society towards involvement of women in political process	$\chi^2=150.822$ (p=0.000)

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigates the social barriers affecting women's political empowerment in Bajaur District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan by using Chi-square (χ^2) analysis. The findings indicate that women’s political empowerment is significantly associated with traditional gender role, purdah (veiling), limited access to resources, restricted mobility and patriarchal norms. Various social barriers such as Purdah, Religious misinterpretation, patriarchy, traditional gender role, and mobility restrictions hinder women’s political participation in study areas. The study highlighted that alone legal provisions are insufficient to accommodate and ensure female participation in political arena. There is a need to raise political awareness through media and campaigns, promote women's education, encourage women's leadership in the political process, ensure access to CNIC, and remove socio-cultural barriers through community involvement. Hence, a comprehensive approach involving state institutions and society is necessary for women's political participation.

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